

Education India

**A Quarterly Refereed Journal
of Dialogues on Education
(ISSN 2278-2435)**

Index

Sl. No.	Paper Title	Author	Page No.
1.	Usage of Mass Media by Youth and its Impact on their Behaviour	Dr. Rajesh Kumar & Dr.Sangeeta Rani	03-17
2.	A Comparative Study of Creativity and Adjustment of Rural and Urban Students at Secondary Level in Guna District	Dr. Sunil Kumar Sain	18-27
3.	Women, Education and Peace – Correlates, Factors and Virtues	Dr.RituBala	28-37
4.	Brainstorming: A Strategy for improving B.Ed. practice teaching	Dr.RasheedaKhatoo n	38-44
5.	The Digital Education Scenario in India	Dr.Aerum Khan, Prof. ChhayaGoel& Prof. DevrajGoel	45-81
6.	A Diagnostics Study of Articles in English Grammar	Dr. Sunil Kumar Sain& Dr.SudhirSudamKa ware	82-98
7.	Educating the Girl Child: Parity, Quality and Equality	ArpanTulsyan	99-108
8.	Promoting Multiculturalism in Blended Learning Environment	RuchiShivam& Dr.Sunita Singh	109-119
9.	Children's Pre-School Participation and the Promise of RTE Act: Evidences and Implications in the Context of the NE States of India	Madhusudan JV	120-136
10.	Where are we Moving? Right to Education Act and its Various Amendments	Dr. Naveen Kumar	137-160
11.	Omnipresence of Wave Particle Duality	Sushanta Saha	161-172

A Quarterly Refereed Journal
of Dialogues on Education
(ISSN 2278-2435)

Paper-3

**Women, Education and Peace – Correlates,
Factors and Virtues**

Dr.RituBala

Women, Education and Peace – Correlates, Factors and Virtues

Dr.RituBala⁴

Abstract

“Sa VidyaYaVimuktaye”.

Though education ‘Vidya’ for peace a theme, a topic, which has drawn a sudden attention of anyone on this planet, this has in fact been very important in all the ages. Peace is virtually important in life. It is a crucial link in the chain of life. It is indispensable for creating atmosphere of mutual understanding and harmony for common development. To maintain peace, the utmost important thing is that the person should have peace of mind, heart and health, hand and socially and economically well adjusted. Education can prove a gateway to peace. A woman is the full circle. Within her is the power to create, nurture and transform. This paper has thrown light on correlates between education, women and peace; factors effecting peace, role of women in Education and how education develops virtues which lead to the state of peace.

Key words: Peace, Education, Women, non-violence, problem-solving attitude, moral values, balanced personality, universal brotherhood

Introduction-

Since ancient times, it is said “Sa VidyaYaVimuktaye” which means with education, we finally attain salvation. Though women, education for peace a theme, a topic, which has drawn a sudden attention of anyone on this planet, this has in fact been very important in all the ages. How? It is but natural if a question like this emerges in one’s mind. To get an appropriate and benefitting reply to this, it is necessary to understand the role of women and comprehend

⁴Assistant Professor, Hindu College of Education, Sonapat, ritu_bala11@yahoo.com

the meaning and nature of peace and education both and that too separately and the correlating factors and virtues.

Peace-

The English word peace has originated from the Latin word 'Pax', which in a broad spectrum means a situation free from strain, civil disorders in particular, struggle quarrel spectrum or conflict along with desiring harmony in day to day human practices. From Eastern view point – India, in particular, the word 'Shanti', made o 'Shant' has originated from Sanskrit, which divulges categorically a wish for freedom from physical, social, natural ad spiritual sufferings. The state of peace has been considered extra ordinary. That is why Shanti occupies a proud place in Vedic prayers, illustrated in 'Shanti Prakram' as predominant maxim (Mool-Mantra) calling for peace in every nook and corner of universe:-

“Om Dyao Shanti Antriksham Shanti Prithvi
Shantirapa Shanti Aushadyay Shanti Vanspataye
Shanti Vishvey Deva Shanti Brahm Shanti Sarvam
Shantireva Shanti Sa Ma Shantirrdhihye
Om Shanti ShantiShanti Om”

“Unto the Heaven be peace, unto the sky and the earth be peace; peace be unto the water, unto the herbs and trees be peace; unto all Gods e peace, unto Brahm and unto all be peace and may we realize that peace.”

Therefore, we can conclude from the both eastern and western views about peace that the state of peace is the source of origin of mutual understating, of co-operation and a clarion call for prosperity of one and all – in the larger interest of humanity.

Education-

Now let us find the answer to the second question, what is and how it is related to peace? The word 'Education', 'Vidya' in Hindi and 'Talim' in Urdu has been

used in many distinct and different senses, i.e. one as to bring up, to nourish, to draw out and second as an act of teaching or training to individual. Most of us have familiarity with the second one. Socrates has rightly said that “Education means the bringing out of the ideas of universal validity which are latent in the mind of every man.” Swami Dyanand has supported the value of education as “Education is a means for character formation and righteous living.” In the words of Mahatma Gandhi, “By education I mean an all-round drawing out of the best in child and man – body, mind and spirit.” Draver, “Education is a process in which and by which knowledge, character and behaviour of the young are shaped and moulded.” According to the Report of Indian Education Commission (1964-66) also emphasized, “Education ought to be related to the life, needs and aspirations of the people and thereby made powerful instrument of social, economic and cultural transformation.”

From these definitions we can conclude that education trains a child to think rationally, develops problem-solving attitude, inculcates the virtues of discipline, truthfulness, honesty, non-violence etc. in the students and forms a basis for the prosperity of the people and the nation. We can conclude in the words of T.P. Nunn, “Education is the complete development of individuality so that he makes an original contribution to human life according to the best of his capacity.”

Woman-

“The fastest way to change society is to mobilize the women of the world.”

- Charles Malik

A woman has the power to give birth, that none others have even dared. It is clear from previous researches and scriptures that woman is a great source of power to create, nurture and destroy the world. Devi Kali, Rani Laxmi Bai, Indira Gandhi, Kalpana Chawla are the few of great examples to support our fact. Mahatma Gandhiji has once said, “Woman is the companion of man, gifted

with equal mental capacity.” The basic unit of society is a woman. As woman makes a family, family makes a home and homes make a society. So we should never think that a virtue may come into existence without the contribution of women. We all know that without education, no development is possible. Here we have forgotten that the very first and best school of a child is its mother’s lap. A good healthy society doesn’t automatically emerge on its own and stands firm but it needs to be emerged and for its emergence women play a pivotal role. In the words of Mother Teresa, “If we have no peace, it is because we have forgotten that we belong to each other.” As her journey through different roles of mother, sister, daughter, mother-in-law, sister-in-law, wife and many more, women have their hands in all aspects of life from behavioral to health education. A woman of high character teaches the virtues of love, care, sympathy, discipline and tolerance. These all are the basic fundamentals which lead to the state of peace. Brigham Young Says, “You educate a man; you educate a man. You educate a woman; you educate a generation.”

Role of Women and Education to Achieve Peace-

“Peace must first be developed (through education) with in an individual. And I believe that love, compassion and atrioms are the fundamental basic for peace. Once these qualities are developed with an individual, he or she is then able to create an atmosphere of peace and harmony. This atmosphere can be expanded and extended from the individual to his/her family, from the family to the community and eventually to the whole world.”

- The 14th Dalai LamaTenzinGyatso

Doubtless peace is virtually important in life. It is a crucial link in the chain of life. It is indispensable for creating atmosphere of mutual understanding and harmony for common development. To maintain peace, the utmost important thing is that the person should have peace of mind, heart and health, hand and socially and economically well adjusted.

Education for peace is a process to achieve the state of peace through means of education and women are best, effective and ideal educationists to provide us education for peace.

Factors - a Curse to Peace-

Let's first recognize the problem why there is need to judge methods to education for peace. In the above discussion we have concluded that education is itself promotes harmonious development of an individual then why even educated persons are also lack this most precious virtue of peace and humanity. We are spending millions and billions to educate our children to make India a developed nation. But to what use? The reason is that we are producing literate machines with no humanity, no feelings and no emotions. We are producing just literate persons but not educated human beings.

Even in the famous Bloom's Taxonomy the objectives has been categorized in three domains: Cognitive, Effective and Conative. But in our most important phase of lesson plans for teaching practice in B.Ed. we just concentrate on cognitive domain of instructional objectives and pay no attention to other two domains. This is the reason that we are just producing literate machines and we have to conduct conferences and seminars on this topic. Our education system is marks and grade oriented not person and humanity oriented. Women in different roles can concentrate on the following internal and external factors that have threats to peace and provide effective solutions to these problems:

Factors - a Bless to Peace-

The factors which contribute to this stage of peace are ahimsa-nonviolence, discipline, mutual understanding, cooperation and coordination, high morals, feeling happy and enlightened, problem solving attitude, tolerance and patience etc. Education – a science and an art of living is a gateway to peace and women have inevitable role in achieving this education. To throw more light on this fact, I put forth the following facts in the support role of woman and education for peace and:

1. Non-Violence ‘Ahimsa’

Yadevisarvabhutesu, Shanti rupenasanthita

Namastasyai, namastasyai, namastasyai, namonamaha!

Peace has its roots in the supreme, eternal and natural human value of non-violence ‘Ahimsa’. Ahimsa is a science for existence and development, an art of living. Education imparts knowledge with the purpose of developing the spirit of duty and responsibility. Education paves the way for conflict resolution with sole interaction of supporting the truth without any confusion or conflict and woman is true symbol of Ahimsa through its tolerance power.

2. Problem-Solving Attitude-

Education develops the problem-solving attitude among students and this attitude helps them to settle inevitable day-to-day problems, disputes and struggles to family, community and society by using the non-violence, peaceful means. A woman can guide her wards about how to solve daily life problems in right and practical manner.

3. Moral Values-

Swami Dyanand has supported the value of education as “Education is a means for character formation and righteous living.” It is the mother in the role of first teacher to her child who can inculcate the moral values like truth, etiquettes, discipline etc. in a practical manner.

4. Balanced Personality-

Woman as a non-formal agency of education is helpful in development of high and strong character and personality by inculcating the qualities of self-control, self –reliance, patience, honesty, truthfulness, dutifulness, honesty, loyalty, justice, punctuality, reality etc. moreover, it deprives off the feeling of jealousy, hate etc.

5. Tolerance and Patience-

Woman and education makes child a qualified and useful citizen of the society from the beginning. She is the true symbol of these virtues. The absence of education leads to conflicts, anxiety and mental disturbance. Education resolves such situations and becomes pioneer to achieve prosperity.

6. VasudevKatumbkam – Universal Brotherhood and Education -

The progress in the field of education is neither the achievement of a single person, society, nation, caste or religion followers only nor is the property of a particular nation. Therefore, education not only spreads the message of national brotherhood but also of vasudevkatumbkam - universal brotherhood. A woman as a source of love and care is capable enough of inculcating values of brotherhood.

From the above discussion, it is proved that education inculcates the virtues of non-violence, problem-solving attitude, discipline, moral values, balanced personality, tolerance, patience and universal brotherhood which lead a person to peace of mind, heart, hand and health and socially and economically well-adjusted and woman may create an atmosphere of mutual understanding and harmony for common development. Therefore it can be evidently declared that

education – a science and an art of living is a gateway to peace and women have inevitable role in achieving this education.

References-

- Bhave, Vinoba (1985). *The Steadfast Wisdom*, SarvaSevaSanghPrakashan, Varanasi.
- Bidyaranya, Swami and Avadhesh Singh (1935). *History of Hindu Mathematics: A Source Book*, MotilalBanarsidas.
- Fernandez, Angelo (1981). *Towards Peace with Justice*, Indian Social Institute, New Delhi.
- Kumar, Ravinder (2012). *Education, Peace and Development*, Kalpaz Publication, New Delhi.
- Kumar, Ravinder (2013). *Facts of Education in Global Perspectives*, The Institute of Indology and Oriental Studies, Shridhar University, Pilani.
- Sachdeva, M.S. and Sharma, K.K. (2003). *Education in the Emerging Indian Society*, Parkash Book Depot, Ludhiana.
- Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopaedia (2014). Retrieved from <http://www.reference.com> dated 05.01.2014.
